

"European Think Tank COREnect Launches Roadmap Towards Leadership in Chips for 6G"

On the 16th of June, the EC published this piece of news: "COREnect has brought together leading experts and policy makers from the telecom and microelectronic sectors in a policy workshop to present its Strategic Research and Innovation (R&I) roadmap. The roadmap outlines strategic actions in three focus areas: Compute & Store, Connect & Communicate, and Sense & Power."

[Read the article](#)

Watch the COREnect Policy Workshop Video

The COREnect Policy Workshop took place on the 16th of June online "An Action Plan for European Leadership in Digital Infrastructures".

[Watch the video](#)

COREnect at The EuCNC

While a mixture of virtual-presence events is now the new reality, COREnect held a physical workshop at the EUCNC and 6G Summit 2022 in Grenoble, France, on the 7th of June.

Get to know how the event was!

[Read](#)

Learn more about the COREnect Roadmap!

How should Europe address future connectivity technologies and achieve European leadership in microelectronics and connectivity with a value-chain approach?

[Roadmap](#)

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